

**DEPICTION OF MARITAL CONFLICTS IN NAYANTARA SAHGAL'S
*STORM IN CHANDIGARH AND THE DAY IN SHADOW***

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ABSTRACT

Nayantara Sahgal's oeuvre is renowned for its political content as well as for being the voice of the Indian educated women who experience a pull between tradition and modernity. The two novels Storm in Chandigarh and The Day in Shadow portray the issue of marital conflicts very distinctly and can be tagged as the emotional autobiographies of Nayantara Sahgal.

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Nayantara's personal agonies, bitterness and the trauma of divorce are mirrored in her novels. Disharmony and dissolution of marriage thus become one of the most prominent themes in her novels. The two novels *Storm in Chandigarh* and *The Day in Shadow* portray the issue of marital conflicts very distinctly and can be tagged as the emotional autobiographies of Nayantara Sahgal. The women protagonists of these two novels are a reflection of Nayantara herself. They belong to high class educated families. They are emancipated women who are aware of their needs and rights. They face the shocking ordeal of a loveless marriage and also suffer the pangs of emotional isolation. The prime causes of their marital conflicts are the clash of their personal values; interpersonal incompatibility; misunderstanding; lack of commitment, respect and trust; loss of individual identity; unmet expectations; dearth of a deeper connection and above all poor communication.

Sahgal reveals the anguish of Indian women who become a victim of the parochial society. In her novel "Storm in Chandigarh", she has highlighted the marital conflicts which occur in the lives of four couples; Inder and Saroj; Jit and Mara; Vishal and Leela; Nikhil and Gauri very realistically and emphatically. The main problem leading to marital conflicts in this novel is discerned as the absence of communication or inability to communicate effectively by the couples. Vishal has never learnt how to communicate with his wife Leela; "He had learned not to share his feelings during a marriage that had turned out to be a vanishing search for communication" (Storm 29). The same problem is seen between Saroj and Inder. There is an absence of communication and mutual conversation which creates viciousness in their relationship. Saroj is unable to speak to Inder without any fear and this is the main problem in their relationship. She points out: "Half the time one is afraid, you know of saying the wrong

thing or of being misunderstood – just of being oneself and being punished for it. So one spends such a lot of time acting or at least hiding, oh that’s very tiring” (Storm 95).

Saroj and Inder the main protagonists of the novel are not happy with each other they are living together just because they are bound by the string of marriage. When Inder goes for a walk with Saroj, she wants to talk to him but Inder is not interested in talking. Saroj says:

“I’ve needed someone to talk to”.... He did not answer. Perhaps it needed none. Perhaps he had understood the great hunger behind it.... “And it’s natural we should need friends who share our interests.”

“What do you mean by friends?” His hand had become wooden in hers.

“People to talk to”.

“Talk about what? What is this mania for talk?”

He took his hand from hers (Storm 207-208).

This is probably one of the reasons why Saroj is drifted towards Vishal, who takes pleasure in talking to her in a friendly manner. Vishal can see that there is no emotional intimacy between Saroj and Inder. During a conversation Saroj tells Vishal, “I am used to it, it’s not being alone I mind, I enjoy that. It’s the loneliness. I’m alone even when Inder is here” (Storm 229). She further says, “I expect he feels that way too” (Storm 229).

Saroj and Inder lack that deeper connection which is an essential ingredient for a happy married life. This is the reason for the widening of the gulf between them. Their relationship is only physical. It seems they are trying to maintain their bond of marriage unwillingly. The expectation of Saroj to get emotional love and intimacy in her married life remains unfulfilled. Many a times she “felt precarious emotional balance between them rock and tilt” (Storm 98). She has surrendered herself to her husband to make her family life peaceful and happy but Inder does not understand her feelings, he nourishes his male ego and all these factors lead to bitterness and bickering between the two.

Another prime cause of their marital discord is due to gender hierarchy which produces inequality. Saroj being an educated woman having impact of western culture expects equality and a liberal atmosphere of freedom which she fails to find in the company of Inder. Gauri and Vishal can recognize this inner urge of Saroj. Vishal says to Gauri that Saroj is like something, “waiting to flower, if it has the chance.” Gauri comments, “She’ll never have a chance at anything if she goes on producing babies” (Storm 167).

The Indian social construct that loss of virginity is evil also contributes in widening the gulf between Saroj and Inder. Inder suppresses Saroj for her pre-marital affair which she had in her college days. When Inder comes to know about it he treats her brutally and considers her a sinner. He tortures her mentally. The author wrote, “The past rose in dreadful images to taunt his manhood. Jealousy had caught him unprepared.... He was maddened by it” (Storm 102). His male ego cannot tolerate it. He behaves badly with Saroj while he has no explanation for his relationship with Mara, wife of Jit. This kind of dual standard ruins relationships.

Mara who is an open minded modern women is acquainted with this sense of superiority which men usually nourish. Their ego is hurt very easily. Mara experiences this when she hurts Inder's ego by saying; "What has Saroj been indulging in "She said lightly, extramarital talk"? He slammed his glass down on the table with a violence that sloshed the liquid onto the carpet. A vein stood out in his temple" (Storm 108).

Mara is also not leading a merry life with her husband Jit. Her aggressive outburst makes it conspicuous;

Mara turned around "which people should talk to each other?"

"Parents and children, husbands and wives."

"Rot, Husbands wouldn't like it a bit if their wives talked to them frankly. That's why women don't" (Storm 139).

Mara and Gauri both lead a free life according to their will trying to maintain their identities as individuals. Gauri is not ready to melt her existence within the warm circle of her husband, Nikhil. She loves Vishal, she seeks pleasure and comfort in her extra marital affair. Vishal is unable to develop a good understanding with his wife Leela and he gets involved in physical relationship with Gauri. Gauri longs for love and attention which she does not get from her husband, Nikhil.

Mara is also not ready to lead a meaningless and bored life with Jit. She is not ready to live an old rotten conventional life of a wife silently. She refuses to submerge her identity into that of her husband. She does not want to live like a pet of her husband but Saroj who is also educated lady remains calm and silent. She feels suffocated in her marital bond but suffers quietly. She tries to assert at times but is suppressed.

The marital dissonance of these protagonists, Saroj, Gauri and Mara attracts them to other men, Gauri meets Vishal in the absence of her husband, Nikhil; Saroj goes on a walk with Vishal when she fails to get this friendliness from her husband Inder. And when Jit goes to Delhi, Mara suffers from loneliness and finds solace in the company of Inder. The search for extra-marital gratification to compensate the hollowness of their marital lives leads these women nowhere. They are not able to resolve any issue which is causing menace in their married life.

The men are equally or even more responsible for creating chaos in their marital relationships. Apart from their indifferent and callous attitude towards their wives; their lack of commitment, stubbornness, pride, anger and inability to negotiate and compromise aggravates the conflicts. These men add fuel to fire by their double standards be it Vishal or Inder. If they cared for the feelings of their wives there would not have been any discord. A good friendly communication and mutual understanding could have solved the conflicts.

Mara and Jit are able to come to an understanding and there is a ray of hope in their relationship. When Jit talks to Mara in a friendly manner, she feels an inner satisfaction. Jit tells her:

“There’s been a silence between us on so many matters. Not that we’ve planned it that way. It has just been taken for granted as the way a couple should behave. No intimacies except in bed. Strange, isn’t it, and yet most people accept marriage in those dried out one-dimensional terms and expect to live almost like strangers” (Storm 238).

Hearing this Mara feels closeness and a sort of comradeship with her husband and says what she had never been able to say before, “I need your help”.

The novel “The Day in Shadow” also deals with marital conflicts and its aftermath that is divorce. In this novel, Nayantara’s personal agonies, traumas and her ghastly experiences are reflected. She herself acknowledges, “In this book I tried to figure out something that has happened to me ... the shattering experience of divorce” (Sahgal 6). Some parts of her own experiences in marriage went in the making of Saroj in “Storm in Chandigarh” but Simrit in “The Day in Shadow” being its culmination is a direct extension of Nayantara. The protagonist of this novel Simrit is an intelligent, sensitive, well informed and well educated woman, she is a writer and a free lance journalist but who is shrewdly trapped in a brutal divorce settlement just like the author herself was in her life.

This novel is about a married couple – Simrit and Som. Their marriage is laden with conflicts which arise due to the fact that Simrit is not ready to submerge her identity into that of her husband, Som, who is uncaring and ruthless. He considers her a mere toy, an object of lust and momentary pleasure. He wants to dominate her just because he gives her financial support. This attitude reveals his male chauvinism, he thinks his wife is his property and he can do whatever he wants with her. He can kiss her without knowing her desire. He can insult her in the presence of his friend.

When the novel begins Simrit and Som are divorced and Simrit is shown battling with the after effects of the divorce. The document of divorce is described as ‘butchery’. The main cause of their conflict was that Som, who was a business magnate was unmindful of his wife as an individual. Simrit aspired for her own identity, she was a well educated woman who wanted freedom, love, warmth, affection and understanding. But Som did not bother about her sentiments. Another cause of their incompatibility was their difference of opinion and preferences. Simrit loved natural beauty, life full of simplicity and freedom while Som loved money, materialistic things and worldly pleasure. Simrit preferred permanence. She says:

I’ve wanted everything to be the same forever, furniture never moved from its place, a never changing address, children growing where tons of things could collect and not be in anybody’s way...and where one could find them years later: toys and souvenirs and old report card, and that sort of thing. Life should be-continuous. Som had had no use for old belongings. He had taken a childish pleasure in newness (Shadow 37).

Som was just the opposite he liked newness in everything, “He kicked the dressing table, “We’ll rid off this hideous thing and all old used junk. We’re moving out of here into a new house” (Shadow 27).

Marriage had become a mockery in their life as there was no companionship and no compatibility. Som's pride, anger, indifference and selfishness had made their life devoid of comradeship. This discourse expresses it clearly:

“I wish, she said passionately we could be friends”

Som scratched his jaw reflectively, “Aren't you being a bit melodramatic?”

“Anyway, whatever you're trying to get at, its quite beyond me” (Shadow 97).

It hampered the effective marriage communication which gradually ended in communication breakdown. Their relationship became so strained that their marital quality was eroded. Simrit was the prime sufferer. Simrit was disgusted beyond endurance she could not tolerate this futile relationship which was devoid of faith, kindness, support understanding respect and emotional connect. She decides to live apart from him in a rented house and set herself free from the humiliation and suppression which she encountered in her wedlock. But separation from her husband does not solve all her problems it rather generates new problems. She, being a divorced woman has to suffer economically, emotionally, socially and psychologically also.

Nayantara Sahgal has been able to depict the marital conflicts so authentically and deftly in these two novels because her own experience of marriage was very bad and shattering. Saroj and Simrit are the two protagonists who epitomize her haunting experiences of a miserable matrimonial bond. In the novel “Storm in Chandigarh” Sahgal has hinted at a very pleasant but demanding solution to the marital conflicts through the dialogue of Vishal when he is chatting with Saroj after a walk with her:

“I wonder why people think decent human relations just happen by luck or by chance”.

“Well, how do they happen?”

“With care, With love, when possible, and otherwise with time and interest. And always with truth, or as much of it as the other person will allow. All of that reduces the heartbreak and a lot of the loneliness of living. But it is damnably hard to do” (Storm 95).

Those who can do it sail swiftly across the sea of marital relationship with bliss, content and peace, combating all fierce and threatening storms that come in the way with the weapons of love, care, faith and compassion.

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